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DETERMINATION OF PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF OIL AND GAS FOR FIELD DEVELOPMENT BY DUAL COMPLETION

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the complete study of the physical properties of oil and gas for the development of the Altyguyi field by dual completion (DC). This study is given for the DC of oil and gas with two elevators in one well.

The article describes in detail the analyses carried out from the selected oil and gas samples to determine temperature, gas factor, buffer pressure, water content, flow rate of productive formations with the creation of a recombined sample and field measurements.

Such work can be useful in the development of multi-layer deposits by the DC method, in order to determine the heterogeneity of oil and gas productive horizons.

Keywords: temperature, flow rate, gas factor, wellhead, water content, dissolved gas, measurement.

To date, the properties of the reservoir oil of the NK_q horizon at the Altyguyi oil and gas field have been studied for six exploration wells (№№ 1, 2, 3, 4, 7 and 10).

Due to the absence of a deep sampler at 4 wells (№№ 2, 3, 4 and 7), studies were carried out with the creation of a recombined sample at the AK IPN-1 installation from the obtained oil and gas samples at the wellhead [1].

The perforated depth of the wells is in the intervals of 3608-3750 meters. Hydrodynamic studies were mainly carried out on 3.4 and 5 mm fittings. The reservoir temperature of the deposit in the range of 90 – 100 °C averages 93.3°C.

During the study of the 4th and 10th wells, the oil flow rate per day was 259,1 m³/day and 166,6 m³/day at wells 1, 2, 3 and 7 was in the range of 33,1-66,7 m³/day.

The field gas factor according to the measurements carried out is different, in the range of 92.0-275.6 m³/m³, on average equal to 163 m³/m³. The water content of productivity of 7-10 wells is 3-7.2%.

Tables 1 and 2 show the results of studies on wells of recombined oil samples from wells 1-10, the values of the main indicators of reservoir oil are determined by calculation.

Table 1

The results of the analysis of oil and gas samples obtained from the wellhead

Well number (object)	Perforation interval (m)	Fitting diameter (m)	Pressure kgf/cm ²			
			P _{buf}	P _{annul}	P _{downh.}	P _{res}
2(I)	3608-3618	4	139	180	395	652
3(I)	3732-3738	4	102	187	355	550
4(I)	3728-3740	5	218	281	482	710
7(II)	3746-3750	3	183	225	560	643
10(I)	3653-3662	8	100	129	305	662
1(I)	3670-3680	5	50	148	263	587

Table 2

The results of analysis of oil and gas samples obtained at the wellhead

Well number (object)	Perforation interval (m)	Fitting diameter (m)	Reservoir temperature °C	Flow rate m ³ /day		% of water	Gas factor m ³ /m ³
				Q _k	Q _w		
2(I)	3608-3618	4	89	45,8	-	170,3	-
3(I)	3732-3738	4	100	33,1	-	178,6	-
4(I)	3728-3740	5	98	259	-	275,6	-
7(II)	3746-3750	3	88	67,7	4,2	92,0	2,9
10(I)	3653-3662	8	95	166	4,1	129,8	7,2
1(I)	3670-3680	5	90	53,4	-	135,0	-

The study of the physical properties of recombined samples was carried out on standard and differential types of degassing.

The main thermodynamic parameters for each well are determined by a decrease in the pressure of 5-6 feet, therefore, more reliable information is obtained with the differential method [2, 3].

In order to substantiate the physical properties of reservoir oil, based on the results of processing the information obtained from the experiments, graphs of the dependence of the volumes of dissolved gas in oil, volume coefficient, dynamic viscosity and density on the saturation pressure are constructed. (Figure 1-4)

Fig. 1. Dependence of the amount of dissolved gas in reservoir oil on saturation pressures

Fig. 2. The dependence of the volume coefficient of oil on the saturation pressure

Fig. 3. Dependence of the dynamic viscosity of oil on reservoir pressure

Fig. 4. Dependence of oil density on saturation pressure in reservoir conditions

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